

THE USE OF GAME CORRECTION IN SPEECH THERAPY WORK WITH CHILDREN WHO HAVE SPEECH DISORDERS

Bakirova Umida Bakhtiyor kizi

Gulistan State University Faculty of Pedagogy 3rd year student

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Speech holidays and entertainment are one of the most relevant types of work in preschool institutions with children with speech disorders. They are based on the basic principles of the program for the education and upbringing of children with general and phonetic-phonemic speech underdevelopment in preschool. This is one of the interesting forms of speech therapy for a child using game correction.

In modern education, not only a certain amount of knowledge, skills and abilities of preschoolers, their correct speech, but also the development of their creative potential, the manifestation of activity in obtaining knowledge, the education of curiosity, the ability to compare, compare, analyze become relevant.

A game is a historically emerging type of activity consisting in the reproduction by children of adult actions, relationships between them and aimed at cognition of the surrounding reality.

Speech holidays and entertainment are one of the most relevant types of work in preschool institutions with children with speech disorders. They are based on the basic principles of the program for the education and upbringing of children with general and phonetic-phonemic speech underdevelopment in preschool.² This is one of the interesting forms of speech therapy for a child using game correction, emotional stimulation.

In the process of speech therapy holidays and entertainment, differentiated assistance to children with developmental disabilities, communication difficulties is especially effective, since it allows solving the problems of speech negativism, shyness.

While preserving the attributes of the game, the emphasis is placed on general education and correctional and educational goals (the development of observation, attention, thinking, education of the correct attitude of children to the team, the desire to participate in a common cause). When selecting competitive tasks, it is necessary to take into account the level of speech and mental capabilities of children. The role of the teacher remains significant throughout the holiday.

To attract the unstable attention of preschoolers to classes is possible only by getting them interested, i.e. to make learning entertaining. The leading activity is the game. Having assessed the level of mental development of children with speech pathology, a list of games is compiled that arouse their greatest interest and make it possible to successfully carry out correctional work.

For children, an activity is a game, and for an adult it is a way of teaching, transferring knowledge, skills and skills to a child, and consolidating them. Actions performed in the game always have a result.

In didactic games, there must be an exciting task, the solution of which requires mental effort, overcoming some difficulties. The words of A.S. Makarenko "A game without effort, a game without active activity is always a bad game" are very appropriate here⁴. By activating thinking, the game affects the emotions of children. The child feels joy from successfully found solutions, quickly and correctly completed tasks. Many games contribute to the replenishment and

activation of the dictionary, the formation of correct sound pronunciation, coherent speech, the ability to express your thoughts correctly.

As the game material (software) accumulates, it can be fixed in the form of speech entertainment. A speech holiday is a celebration that unites children with a community of experiences, emotionality. The structure of entertainment is developed taking into account the knowledge of children, alternating games, tasks, musical pauses so that the children do not lose interest.

Speech holidays can be held at the beginning of the year (for example, in the form of speech entertainment "Let's get acquainted", "Understand me"), in the middle of the year (as the defective sounds are set: "Journey to the country of Lapland, Normandy", etc.), at the end of the year: "I am a polymath", "Field of Miracles", "Celebration of correct speech". All participants of the correctional and educational process can be involved in the speech festival: parents, educators, musical directors.

The educational value of speech holidays and entertainment is very great. They contribute to the development of activity, independence, self-confidence. The obstacles that prevent the child from actively manifesting himself in the team disappear, uncertainty and indecision disappear. The child achieves his goal, acts together with his comrades.

The fulfillment of the conditions of the game and compliance with the rules require the child's concentrated attention, observation, memorization and reproduction. This brings the game closer to learning. Children really like puzzles and crosswords that help them learn sound analysis in a playful way.

Games are included in all parts of entertainment and adhere to the main tasks: diagnostic, cognitive, entertaining, correctional. Various games are suitable for entertainment (sports - of a competitive nature; didactic; cognitive; psychological; joke games).

Competitive games:

- "Who will assemble the whole from the parts faster"
- "Who will name more..."
- "Who will remember more objects and name them"
- "Who will pronounce a clean tongue more expressively, a tongue twister"

Games for the formation of coherent speech:

- Magic Chair"
- "Readers' Contest"
- "Tell me about your mom (about yourself)"
- "Convey kindness"
- "Continue the sentence"
- "Proverbs, sayings, tongue twisters"
- "What does the letter look like"
- "Who's bigger?"
- "Collect the beads"
- "Words got mixed up"

Games for the formation of arbitrary attention:

- "Find the letters", "Name the objects"
- "Underline A, strike out O"
- "Find the differences"

- "I am a word; you are many words"
- "What did the artist mix up?"
- "Help the postman Tishka"

"Speech holidays are a good way to consolidate and apply the acquired knowledge and skills, self-affirmation of children."

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